

1 **An experimental immune activation regimen targeting a receptor activated in CNS metastasis,**
2 **Prss8.**

3 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
4 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

5 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

6 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

7 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

8 East Islip, NY USA 11730

- 9 1. Metastasis to the brain occurs in a significant fraction of patients with breast cancer (1-3).
10 2. We mined published RNA-sequencing and microarray data (4, 5) to compare primary and
11 metastatic tumor transcriptomes for the discovery of genes associated with metastasis to the central
12 nervous system (CNS, including the brain) in humans with breast cancer.
13 3. We found that serine protease 8, encoded by *Prss8*, was among the genes whose expression was
14 most different in the brain metastases of patients with metastatic breast cancer as a second type of
15 metastasis, pulmonary metastases (metastasis to the lung).
16 4. *Prss8* mRNA was among the gene products present at highest quantity and most increased
17 quantities in CNS metastases as compared to lung metastases.
18 5. We concluded that modulation of *Prss8* expression may be relevant to the biology by which tumor
19 cells metastasize from the breast to the CNS in humans with metastatic breast cancer.
20 6. The alarmingly high rate of central nervous system metastasis occurring in patients with solid
21 tumors including cancer of the breast and lung (1-3) demands an enhanced understanding of the
22 transcriptional makeup of brain metastatic tissues to support identification of therapeutic targets.
23 7. We performed a comparative transcriptome analysis of primary and metastatic tumors in patients
24 with brain metastatic breast cancer using published RNA-sequencing data (4).
25 8. We also utilized a separate, published microarray gene expression dataset (5) to determine if
26 target differential expression was a shared feature of CNS metastasis among patients with breast cancer.
27 9. We present our findings here together with data supporting approval of Compassionate Use
28 Protocol complaint for the use of an investigational agent (under development) that targets *Prss8*.
1. We assume activation of the immune cell surface marker silences or significantly suppresses a
local immune response that is specifically anti-tumor.
2. As such, we expect a monoclonal antibody targeting *Prss8* to activate endogenous anti-tumor
defense. The magnitude of this activation is not yet understood.
3. High tumor expression of *Prss8* in humans is correlated with more rapid metastasis to a distant
organ site (Figure 1).
4. The complete regimen in its initial formulation also contains monoclonal antibodies that target
5. PD-1,
6. PD-L1 and
7. CTLA4 to maximize endogenous anti-tumor response.
8. The FDA Compassionate Use Protocol outlined here is for patients whose disease has
progressed following treatment for CNS metastatic breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, “regional” metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the CNS to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the CNS metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: Prss8.

Results

Figure 1: Prss8 is differentially expressed in CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. CNS metastases in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.

n=5 CNS metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
5652	2.89e04	0.521	3.625016	1.887614	7183.62	Prss8	227/22,997	99.0

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CNS metastases and lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of serine protease 8, encoded by *Prss8* in metastasis to the CNS in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *Prss8* changed more than 99% of the human CNS metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of *Prss8* messenger RNA in CNS metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *Prss8* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of *Prss8* likely defined the CNS metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of *Prss8*, immunoglobulin- or small molecule-based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with CNS metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of CNS metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

References

1. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Siegel, P.M., Bos, P.D., Shu, W., Giri, D.D., Viale, A., Olshen, A.B., Gerald, W.L. and Massagué, J., 2005. Genes that mediate breast cancer metastasis to lung. *Nature*, 436(7050), pp.518-524.
2. Zardavas, D., Irrthum, A., Swanton, C. and Piccart, M., 2015. Clinical management of breast cancer heterogeneity. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 12(7), pp.381-394.
3. Poste, G., Tzeng, J., Doll, J., Greig, R., Rieman, D. and Zeidman, I., 1982. Evolution of tumor cell heterogeneity during progressive growth of individual lung metastases. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 79(21), pp.6574-6578.
4. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Padua, D., Bos, P., Nguyen, D.X., Nuyten, D., Kreike, B., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Ishwaran, H. and Foekens, J.A., 2007. Lung metastasis genes couple breast tumor size and metastatic spread. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(16), pp.6740-6745.
5. Brown, D.M. and Ruoslahti, E., 2004. Metadherin, a cell surface protein in breast tumors that mediates lung metastasis. *Cancer cell*, 5(4), pp.365-374.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. GSE191230: Ong, L.T., Lee, W.C., Ma, S., Oguz, G., Niu, Z., Bao, Y., Yusuf, M., Lee, P.L., Goh, J.Y., Wang, P. and Yong, K.S.M., 2022. IFI16-dependent STING signaling is a crucial regulator of anti-HER2 immune response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(31), p.e2201376119.
10. GSE56493: Tobin, N.P., Lundberg, A., Lindström, L.S., Harrell, J.C., Foukakis, T., Carlsson, L., Einbeigi, Z., Linderholm, B.K., Loman, N., Malmberg, M. and Fernö, M., 2017. PAM50 provides prognostic information when applied to the lymph node metastases of advanced breast cancer patients. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 23(23), pp.7225-7231,:
11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE191230 (9) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in metastasis to the CNS (central nervous system) in humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.

1 **Differential expression of serine protease 8 in cancers of the breast.**

2 Shahan Mamoor, MS¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 East Islip, NY 11730

5 Breast cancer affects women at relatively high frequency (1). We mined published microarray datasets (2,
6 3) to determine in an unbiased fashion and at the level of the transcriptome genes most differentially
7 expressed in the primary tumors of patients with early-onset breast cancer. We found significant
8 differential expression of the gene encoding serine protease 8, PRSS8, when comparing primary tumors of
9 the breast to the tissue of origin, the normal breast: in women aged 45 and younger, and women aged 70
10 and higher. PRSS8 mRNA was present at significantly higher quantities in tumors of the breast as
11 compared to normal breast tissue. Analysis of human survival data revealed that expression of PRSS8 in
12 primary tumors of the breast was correlated with overall survival in patients with luminal B subtype breast
13 cancer, demonstrating a relationship between primary tumor expression of a differentially expressed gene
14 and patient survival outcomes influenced by PAM50 molecular subtype. PRSS8 may be of relevance to
15 initiation, maintenance or progression of cancers of the female breast.

16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26 Keywords: breast cancer, PRSS8, serine protease 8, systems biology of breast cancer, targeted therapeutics
27 in breast cancer.

1 Invasive breast cancer is diagnosed in over a quarter of a million women in the United States each
2 year and in 2018, breast cancer was the leading cause of cancer death in women worldwide (4-6). While
3 patients with localized breast cancer are provided a 99% 5-year survival rate, patients with regional breast
4 cancer, cancer that has spread to lymph nodes or nearby structures, are provided an 86% 5-year survival
5 rate (5). Patients with metastasis to distant sites, like the brain, are provided a 27% 5-year survival rate
6 (5). Understanding how primary tumors are most transcriptionally different from the tissue from which
7 they originate, the breast, can facilitate development of novel diagnostic and therapeutics to promote early
8 detection and enhanced treatment, and contribute to efforts to prevent progression to metastatic stages. We
9 mined published microarray data (2, 3) to understand at the transcriptome level and in an unbiased fashion
10 genes most differentially expressed in primary tumors of the breast as compared to normal breast tissue for
11 discovery and validation of novel therapeutic targets.

8 **Methods**

9 We utilized datasets GSE42568 (2) and GSE109169 (3) for this global differential gene expression
10 analysis of female breast cancer in conjunction with GEO2R. GSE42568 was generated using Affymetrix
11 Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 array technology with $n=17$ normal breast tissue biopsies and $n=11$
12 primary breast tumor biopsies from patients with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform
13 GPL570; all patients were at or below the age of 45. We also compared $n=17$ normal breast tissue
14 biopsies against $n=22$ primary breast tumor biopsies from patients with breast cancer, all of which were at
15 or above the age of 70. GSE109169 was generated using Affymetrix Human Exon 1.0 ST Array
16 technology with $n=25$ normal breast tissue and $n=25$ tumors of the breast; analysis was performed using
17 platform GPL5175. The tissues whose expression was profiled in this dataset are paired tissues (25
18 tumors matching 25 breast tissues from 25 patients). The Benjamini-Hochberg method of p -value
19 adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p -values were used to assess statistical
20 significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI
21 generated category of platform annotation was used. A statistical test was performed to evaluate whether
22 PRSS8 expression was significantly different between primary breast tumors and normal breast tissue
23 using a two-tailed t-test. For Kaplan-Meier survival analysis, we used the Kaplan-Meier plotter tool (7) for
24 correlation of PRSS8 mRNA expression levels with overall survival (OS) in $n=1879$ patients with
25 breast cancer (all molecular subtypes considered together), $n=431$ patients with basal-like subtype cancer,
26 $n=596$ patients with luminal A subtype cancer, $n=439$ patients with luminal B subtype cancer, $n=362$
27 patients with HER2+ subtype cancer, and $n=51$ patients with normal-like subtype cancer.

20 **Results**

21 We performed discovery of genes associated with breast cancer in females through blind, whole
22 tumor transcriptome analysis using independently published microarray datasets (2, 3).

23 **PRSS8 is differentially expressed in primary tumors of the breast.**

24 Studying the global gene expression profiles of 22 primary breast cancers from patients aged 31 to
25 45 revealed that the gene encoding serine protease 8, PRSS8, was among the genes most differentially
26 expressed in tumors of the breast in females with early onset-breast cancer (Chart 1). When sorting each
27 of the genes expressed in tumors of the breast in human early-onset breast cancer based on significance of
28 magnitude of difference as compared to normal breast tissue, PRSS8 ranked 20 out of 54675 total
transcripts, equating to 99.96% differential expression (Chart 1). Differential expression of PRSS8 in
early-onset breast cancer was statistically significant (Chart 1; $p=2.31E-10$).

1 We used the same microarray dataset (2) to discover the most significant transcriptional changes in
2 $n=22$ primary breast tumors of women age 70 and greater. In older women, differential expression of
3 PRSS8 ranked 27 out of 54675 total transcripts, equating to 99.95% differential expression (Chart 2).
4 Differential expression of PRSS8 in female breast cancer (age 70 and higher) was statistically significant
(Chart 2; $p=5.59E-14$). Thus, differential expression of PRSS8 was a conserved gene expression change
5 in female breast cancer, in women aged 70 and above, and in early-onset breast cancer.

6 We interrogated a second microarray dataset (3) for target validation, here studying global gene
7 expression patterns in the tumors of 25 patients with early-onset breast cancer, which again revealed
8 significant differential expression of PRSS8 in human breast cancer (Chart 3). When sorting each of the
9 genes expressed in the tumors of patients with breast cancer based on significance of difference as
10 compared to normal breast tissue, PRSS8 ranked 1310 out of 19076 total transcripts, equating to 93.1%
11 differential expression (Chart 3). Differential expression of PRSS8 in the tumors of patients with breast
12 cancer was statistically significant (Chart 3; $p=3.56E-08$). These data suggested that differential
13 expression of PRSS8 was not an artifact of a single microarray dataset, nor was it strictly associated with
14 early-onset breast cancer, rather a general feature of cancers of the breast, and could be observed
15 cross-laboratory.

16 **PRSS8 is expressed at significantly higher levels in breast tumors as compared to the breast.**

17 We obtained exact mRNA expression levels for PRSS8 from the breast and from breast tumors to
18 understand the magnitude and direction of PRSS8 expression change. PRSS8 was expressed at higher
19 quantities in tumors of the breast as compared to normal breast tissue (Figure 1). Increased expression of
20 PRSS8 in primary breast tumors was statistically significant (Figure 1: $p<0.0001$). PRSS8 was expressed
21 at 3.65 ± 0.98 arbitrary units (AU) in normal breast tissue, while it was expressed at 7.21 ± 0.91 AU in
22 tumors of the breast in early-onset breast cancer. We calculated a mean fold change of 1.98 in PRSS8
23 mRNA levels when comparing primary tumors of the breast to normal breast tissues.

24 **PRSS8 expression correlates with survival outcomes in luminal B subtype human breast cancer.**

25 We performed Kaplan-Meier survival analysis (7) to study relationships between tumor PRSS8
26 mRNA expression levels and survival outcomes in patients with breast cancer. We observed a correlation
27 between PRSS8 expression and overall survival (OS) in patients with luminal B subtype breast cancer
28 which trended towards statistical significance (Figure 2; log rank p -value: 0.09 for overall survival, hazard
ratio: 1.36 (0.95-1.94)). PRSS8 mRNA levels were a negative prognostic indicator in luminal B subtype
breast cancer patients. Median OS was 205.64 months for luminal B patients with low tumor expression
of PRSS8 while median OS was 197.62 months for luminal B patients with high tumor expression of
PRSS8 (Chart 4).

PRSS8 primary tumor expression was not correlated with overall survival in all patients with breast
cancer (irrespective of molecular subtype) (Figure 2; log rank p -value: 0.26 for OS, hazard ratio: 1.11
(0.92-1.34)), in patients with basal-like breast cancer (Figure 2; log rank p -value: 0.5 for OS, hazard ratio:
1.14 (0.78-1.67)), in patients with luminal A subtype breast cancer (Figure 2; log rank p -value: 0.41 for
OS, hazard ratio: 1.19 (0.78-1.83)), in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (Figure 2; log rank p -value: 0.31
for OS, hazard ratio: 1.22 (0.83-1.79)) or in patients with normal-like breast cancer (Figure 2; log rank
 p -value: 0.5 for OS, hazard ratio: 0.71 (0.27-1.92)).

Thus, through comparative transcriptome analysis of primary tumors of the breast and normal
breast tissue, we found that differential expression of PRSS8 was among the most significant
transcriptional features of primary tumors from women with early-onset breast cancer. PRSS8 expression

1 in primary tumors of the breast was correlated with overall survival in patients with luminal B subtype
2 disease, with mRNA levels of PRSS8 a negative prognostic indicator for luminal B breast cancer patients.

3 **Discussion**

4 Invasive breast cancer is a medical problem with a 27% 5-year survival rate for women whose
5 disease has spread to distant sites (5, 6). To facilitate understanding of the basic transcriptional differences
6 between primary tumors of the breast and the tissues from which these tumors originate, normal breast
7 tissues, we performed comparative transcriptome analysis using two independently published microarray
8 datasets (2, 3), providing evidence here that differential expression of serine protease 8, encoded by
9 PRSS8, is a defining transcriptional feature of human breast cancer: in early onset-breast cancer, and in the
10 primary tumors of women aged 70 and higher. PRSS8 was expressed at significantly higher levels in
11 primary tumors from patients with breast cancer as compared to normal breast tissue. Importantly, in
12 patients with luminal B subtype breast cancers, expression of PRSS8 was correlated with overall survival.
13 These data collectively will provide high-quality molecular portraits (8) and serve as a basis for therapeutic
14 target validation and pipeline development in human breast cancer.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Britt, K.L., Cuzick, J. and Phillips, K.A., 2020. Key steps for effective breast cancer prevention. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 20(8), pp.417-436.
2. Clarke, C., Madden, S.F., Doolan, P., Aherne, S.T., Joyce, H., O'driscoll, L., Gallagher, W.M., Hennessy, B.T., Moriarty, M., Crown, J. and Kennedy, S., 2013. Correlating transcriptional networks to breast cancer survival: a large-scale coexpression analysis. *Carcinogenesis*, 34(10), pp.2300-2308.
3. Chang, J.W., Kuo, W.H., Lin, C.M., Chen, W.L., Chan, S.H., Chiu, M.F., Chang, I., Jiang, S.S., Tsai, F.Y., Chen, C.H. and Huang, P.H., 2018. Wild-type p53 upregulates an early onset breast cancer-associated gene GAS7 to suppress metastasis via GAS7–CYFIP1-mediated signaling pathway. *Oncogene*, 37(30), pp.4137-4150.
4. Bray, F., Ferlay, J., Soerjomataram, I., Siegel, R.L., Torre, L.A. and Jemal, A., 2018. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, 68(6), pp.394-424.
5. DeSantis, C.E., Ma, J., Gaudet, M.M., Newman, L.A., Miller, K.D., Goding Sauer, A., Jemal, A. and Siegel, R.L., 2019. Breast cancer statistics, 2019. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, 69(6), pp.438-451.
6. Bilani, N., Zabor, E.C., Elson, L., Elimimian, E.B. and Nahleh, Z., 2020. Breast cancer in the United States: a cross-sectional overview. *Journal of cancer epidemiology*, 2020.
7. Györfy, B., 2021. Survival analysis across the entire transcriptome identifies biomarkers with the highest prognostic power in breast cancer. *Computational and structural biotechnology journal*, 19, pp.4101-4109.
8. Perou, C.M., Sørlie, T., Eisen, M.B., Van De Rijn, M., Jeffrey, S.S., Rees, C.A., Pollack, J.R., Ross, D.T., Johnsen, H., Akslén, L.A. and Fluge, Ø., 2000. Molecular portraits of human breast tumours. *Nature*, 406(6797), pp.747-752.

1 Rank: 20
2 Probe ID: 202525_at
3 p-value: 2.31E-10
4 t: -9.8
5 B: 13.66042343
6 Gene: PRSS8
7 Gene name: serine protease 8

8 **Chart 1: PRSS8 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with early-onset breast cancer.**

9 Rank of differential expression, probe ID, p-value of global differential expression, t, a moderated
10 t-statistic, B, the log-odds of differential expression between the groups compared, gene and gene name
11 are listed in this chart.

12 Rank: 27
13 Probe ID: 202525_at
14 p-value: 5.59E-14
15 t: -1.15E+01
16 B: 21.719588
17 Gene: PRSS8
18 Gene name: serine protease 8

19 **Chart 2: PRSS8 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with breast cancer, age 70 and higher.**

20 Rank of differential expression, probe ID, p-value of global differential expression, t, a moderated
21 t-statistic, B, the log-odds of differential expression between the groups compared, gene and gene name
22 are listed in this chart.
23
24
25
26
27
28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Rank: 1310
Probe ID: 3688254
p-value: 3.56E-08
t: -6.48
B: 8.462624
Gene: PRSS8
Gene name: serine protease 8

Chart 3: PRSS8 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with early-onset human breast cancer.

Rank of differential expression, probe ID, p-value of global differential expression, t, a moderated t-statistic, B, the log-odds of differential expression between the groups compared, gene and gene name are listed in this chart.

Figure 1: PRSS8 is expressed at significantly higher levels in primary breast tumors as compared to normal breast tissue.

The mRNA expression level of PRSS8 in normal breast tissue (left) and in primary tumors of the breast (right) is graphically depicted with the result of a statistical test evaluating significance of difference in PRSS8 expression between normal breast tissue and primary tumors of the breast, a p -value, listed above.

Figure 2: PRSS8 expression correlates with overall survival in patients with luminal B subtype breast cancer, but not in patients with basal, luminal A, HER2+, or normal-like subtype cancer.

Depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots is the probability of overall survival (OS) for $n=1879$ patients with breast cancer (all molecular subtypes considered together) (above, left), for $n=431$ patients with basal-like breast cancer (above, middle), $n=362$ patients with HER2+ breast cancer (above, right), $n=596$ patients with luminal A breast cancer (below, left), $n=439$ patients with luminal B breast cancer (below, middle), and $n=51$ patients with normal-like breast cancer (below, right) stratified into two groups, based on low or high expression of PRSS8 in patient primary tumors. The log rank p -value denoting statistical significance of difference in overall survival when comparing the two groups, as well as hazard ratio for this comparison is listed above. Listed below is the number of patients at risk (number of patients alive) per interval, after stratification based on PRSS8 expression; in the first interval, number at risk is number of patients alive; in each subsequent interval, number at risk is the number at risk less those who have expired or are censored.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Luminal B patients

Low PRSS8 expression: 205.64 months

High PRSS8 expression: 197.62 months

Chart 4: In luminal B subtype breast cancer, median overall survival is superior in patients with low primary tumor expression of PRSS8.

The overall survival of $n=439$ luminal B subtype breast cancer patients based on stratification into low or high tumor expression of PRSS8 is listed in this chart.